

Organizational Values in Practices

Value (L1)	Instantiation (L3)
People-centric	<p>OINS-1 Take Care of Colleagues (..when planning the work, we consider the well-being of the developers..) [ID3], (..every single day, my colleagues are taking care of me..) [ID4], (..we take care of our colleagues, where we enjoy a good work environment that we co-create..) [ID5], (..takes care of the workers..) [ID6]</p>
	<p>OINS-2 Focus on User's Impact (...we also consider the impact that our work will have on the user..) [ID3], (...we develop and maintain tools oriented to our internal users with the goal of making their job easier...) [ID8], (...putting the fit of what we build in the center of the activity..) [ID1]</p>
Challenge-centric	<p>OINS-3 Take Challenging Task (..we don't shy away from tasks outside our comfort zone..) [ID1], (..we are motivated by challenges...), (..we are all the time being challenged with new projects..) [ID4].</p>
	<p>OINS-4 Strive for Innovation (..we constantly strive to create innovative products and enjoy undertaking new projects..) [ID3], (...presents a new technology... my team included a bunch of such last year into the daily development..) [ID5], (..we are constantly looking for ways to innovate the product and improve technologically...) [ID8].</p>
	<p>OINS-5 Adapt to User's Request (..can grow and adapt to customer requests..) [ID6]</p>
Change-centric	<p>OINS-6 Embrace Changes in Organization (..company changes a lot and it impacts the day to day. new roles, new circles (sociocracy), new ways of doing, new tools, new customers, new partnerships..) [ID4], (...In the almost X years that I've been working here, I've experienced all kinds of changes (changes in team names, etc...) [ID8]</p>
	<p>OINS-7 Reflect and Continuously Improve (..we learn, we grow, we look back on what we did/achieve, we look for new directions of improvement..) [ID5], (..continuous improvement..) [ID6]</p>
	<p>OINS-8 Adapt to Change (..adapt to changes as they come..) [ID1], (..given the rapid evolution of the industry, we constantly need to be flexible and adjust our course if necessary..) [ID3], (..we are open to change.. we work with rapid adaptation and without fear of change..) [ID5]</p>
	<p>OINS-3 Take a Challenging Task (..my team and I frequently express the interest in picking the most difficult and important problems we have at hand, and try to solve them. We are happy to present those to other teams as well..) [ID7]</p>
Team-centric	<p>OINS-1 Take Care of Colleagues (...take care of each other's well-being by thinking first on the sustainability of what we do..) [ID1]</p>
	<p>OINS-9 Build Strong Bond (..one of the greatest assets of our team is the strong relationships and trust among its members..) [ID3], (...the company has extraordinary people who are passionate about what they do and I see that in the different sessions we have together...) [ID8], (..We investigate a lot in and outside of our working hours, and share cool stuff..) [ID7]</p>
	<p>OINS-10 Work Together (..we enjoy the feedback between people, and we grow with it..) [ID4], (..work together, works better..) [ID6]</p>